

“DEAR USER...”

EMPATHY BUILDING METHODS FOR ASSISTIVE PRODUCT DESIGN

Ana Correia de Barros and Carlos Duarte
Universidade da Beira Interior, UNIDCOM/IADE
ana.correia.barros@iade.pt, carlos.duarte@iade.pt

ABSTRACT

Empathizing with users, many authors argue, is especially important in assistive product design, and participatory design is, amongst other things, highly efficient in eliciting designer-user empathy. However, participatory design demands expenses and resources which are not always available. This paper describes a workshop with graduating design students in which alternative methods were devised and combined to foster designer-user empathy. The methods were found to have been successful both in empathy eliciting and, furthermore, in raising students' sense of social responsibility, and are thus presented as a possible alternative to tackle, to some extent, the concerns associated to the use of participatory design.

Keywords: design education, empathy, disability, methods.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid demographic increase of the older population is a phenomenon which is concerning many sectors of society (Manning, et al., 2011). This increase will bring about issues of dependence which, some authors agree, could be tackled by promoting the use of assistive products (APs). The use of APs might not only reduce hours of personal help, but also help people maintain their independence (Hoening, et al., 2003). The World Health Organization's (2008) projections for 2030 are that one of the main causes for Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) will be stroke. Indeed, stroke is already today one of the major causes for dependence all over the world (EUSI, 2003).

This increase in the number of people who will be living with impairments and disabilities poses a challenge for design, in that designers will be called to devise products – assistive and inclusive ones – to meet these needs.

However, designing inclusive and assistive products is a great challenge in itself. Apart from functional user requirements, emotional requirements are an especially important issue when designing for people with disabilities in mind. When looking into the literature about AP rejection and abandonment, one can notice that a good part of the reasons underlying these undesired phenomena are psychosocial ones (Correia de Barros, et al., 2011a).

On the other hand, these products can be quite expensive and statistics show that there is a correlation between disability and poverty (Traustadóttir and Rice, 2012). Thus, designing appropriate APs may in some cases mean to design these APs so that they are affordable as well.

Hence, there is a need for better and more suited products to meet people with disabilities' emotional requirements. One of the starting points to initiate this turn could be by working with future designers while they are still receiving their formal education so as to prepare them to address these demands. Designing products with people with disabilities in mind is particularly difficult for designers, for they find it difficult to anticipate the needs of this particular group, since their life experiences are often very far apart from those of the users they are designing for (Nicolle, 1999). In order to be able to anticipate these needs,

designers must be able to understand the users. This, according to many authors, will be possible through empathy building (McDonagh, Thomas, et al., 2009).

While Ortony et al. (1988) state that empathy is not an emotion, but rather that there are emotions which arise through empathy building, Eisenberg et al. (2010) define it as an affective response which emerges through the understanding of how other people feel in a given situation. Furthermore, according to Eisenberg et al. (1999) empathy most likely contributes to prosocial behavior oriented to others, being prosocial behavior defined as “voluntary behavior intended to benefit another” (p. 1360).

RESONATING WITH USERS' NEEDS

Interaction with products is part of a greater system, as argued by Forlizzi (2007), who has introduced the concept of *product ecologies* into design research. This concept and framework is particularly important for understanding users' emotional responses to specific products in specific contexts. Forlizzi's framework comprises 4 different systems to consider when trying to understand product interaction. The first system of interactions accounts for the individual and his/her history, the second is about the immediate context, the third accounts for the community, and the fourth includes higher-level concerns related to the culture within which interaction takes place.

So, beyond including users in the design process it would be of utmost importance to consider the user holistically, i.e. having conducted previous research to understand the user within all the four levels. This approach would be very valuable to identify concerns that could be used to design for positive emotional responses towards the product. As argued by other authors, understanding users' concerns is crucial to anticipate appraisals and, consequently, to design for positive emotions (Desmet, Overbeek et al. 2001; Desmet and Dijkhuis 2003).

The issue of emotional response is gaining ever more importance in design research and practice, particularly amongst Inclusive Design advocates, given that people with disabilities face stigmatization problems which are often extensible to the APs they make use of (Næss and Øritsland 2005; Pullin 2009).

Recently, Storni (2010) has presented proof that users appropriate APs in very personal and particular ways according to their needs. This finding has led the author to suggest the use of participatory design in the development of APs, so that users might have a say in what their APs should be like and respond to, and not having to come up with contraptions later on to solve problems that were left unsolved by designers.

The use of participatory design techniques is argued by many authors to be one of the best methods to use when developing products to be used by people with disabilities (Demirbilek and Demirkan, 2004; Dong, Clarkson, et al., 2005; Storni, 2010). Beyond involving users from onset at the design process, participatory design is said to allow designers to empathize with users, thus enabling the latter to better understand the needs of the first. The downside of participatory design is that it is demanding regarding time, money and logistics, which are often not available.

The *persona's* approach (Pruitt and Adlin, 2006) might help tackle this downside while still being able to elicit empathy with users. However, we hypothesized that personas, due to gathering data from several users into fictitious ones, might weaken one important intensity variable (Ortony, et al., 1988) affecting emotions – *sense of reality*.

In the next sections of this paper we will be describing the testing of methods conducted under the form of a workshop with undergraduate 3rd year design students, which sought to tackle the above mentioned downsides of the two approaches by trying, with few resources, to elicit empathy between designers and users.

This conviction for the need to elicit empathy was brought about after an analysis to a previous workshop with another group of 3rd year design students, which was found to have failed due to lack of empathy building (Correia de Barros, et al., 2011b). At this earlier workshop we had distributed a list of guidelines for the design of APs which we had previously produced from our research. The students paid little attention to these guidelines and we hypothesized that lack of empathy building might have

been the cause underlying their little account for the guidelines – and thus, lack of sense of responsibility towards their role as designers in other people's lives.

METHODS

The workshop was held for two weeks (28h in total) with a class of 20 3rd year design students from the Design III course, which focuses on industrial design. Most work was done in class, except for task simulation and product testing which was started in class and completed at home. Students were divided into 5 groups of 4 elements each, and personas were randomly distributed – one per group. At the end of the workshop students were sent a questionnaire to assess the efficiency of the methods we had employed for empathy building and to validate the use of the guidelines for AP design.

Our approach consisted in the adoption and combination of four methodologies: an adaptation to the persona's approach, the use of storytelling, simulation and product testing, and the writing of letters to users.

PERSONAS

Our previous research has focused on stroke victims and data collection was made in the form of semi-structured interviews to 101 stroke victims (Correia de Barros, n.d.). After a thorough analysis to stroke victims' needs, expectations and preferences regarding APs, we were left with a wide range of information which we used to create personas for this particular workshop. However, instead of gathering data from the majority of stroke victims into fictitious ones, we opted by creating personas which described individual and particular cases we came across with during our research. Due to privacy issues we have changed personal data for each persona (e.g. name, picture, city), but we maintained the real problems they had described. Each persona presented a sentence stated by the person – in some cases these were transcribed verbatim, and in others these sentences were fabricated from the notes we had taken about each stroke victim during the interviews. In the end we had 5 different personas – what they all had in common was hemiplegia and a low monthly income.

This use of real cases was expected to foster students' empathy towards the personas they would be working for and to test whether or not students could address emotional issues and intertwine them with other relevant ones in AP ecologies (Forlizzi, 2007), such as product price.

STORYTELLING

We have also hypothesized that in as much as fiction writing has the ability to foster empathy by acting upon the intensity variables of *strength of cognitive unit* and *sense of reality* (Ortony, et al., 1988), the adoption of storytelling, which is not strange to design (Erickson, 1995; Kouprie and Sleeswijk Visser, 2009), would help potentiate the effect of personas. Hence, we used storytelling throughout the workshop – starting with its use during the workshop presentation by sharing stories of real stroke victims – and we encouraged students to adopt this method throughout their successive presentations of the work progress to the class. Indeed, the workshop comprised continuous sessions of oral presentations of each group's work to the class so that every student would have a chance to participate in every project being developed.

SIMULATION AND PRODUCT TESTING

Simulation of user capabilities is widely used in inclusive and assistive product design, ranging from more complex to less complex techniques (Cardoso and Clarkson, 2012). Beyond allowing designers to understand the experience of others, it might also help raise "empathetic emotions" (Ortony, et al., 1988) in designers by putting themselves in users' shoes. We found this method to be fundamental for the workshop at both levels.

Simulation was made at four stages: simulating task performance using one hand alone, simulation using movement restrictors (e.g. gloves), testing of existing APs using one hand and the movement restrictors, and final testing of solutions designed by the students using one hand alone and movement restrictors.

LETTER

The final method we devised was aimed at further strengthening the above mentioned intensity variables. We let students know that they would be asked to write a letter to the user they had worked for

at the end of the workshop. In this letter they were asked to state what they had done for the user, what were the issues they had considered along the way, their challenges, and how they expected to have contributed to the user's quality of life.

According to Kouprie and Sleeswijk Visser (2009), there are four phases to 'empathic design': discovery, immersion, connection and detachment. During the first the designer discovers the world of the other, then he or she immerses in it by stepping into the user's shoes, the designer establishes emotional connections by the stage of 'connection' and finally he steps out – the designer detaches himself or herself from the user's world – so that he or she will be able to use his or her technical knowledge and design skills to solve the problem.

Our intention when asking students to write the letter (and letting them know this from the workshop's first session) was to prevent students from being too detached from the people they would be working for. The goal was that students would never forget that they were using their design skills for other persons' sake, i.e. in benefit of others. We hypothesized that the letter would increase the variables of *strength of cognitive unit* and *sense of reality* and that, in so doing, would be able to have this effect of constant reminder of their social responsibility.

THE WORKSHOP

In the introductory session students were informed about the aims of the workshop, and were then taken through the process of storytelling about stroke victims' lives and common concerns, and through stories on a collection of telling examples about the importance of emotional issues in the interaction of stroke victims with objects surrounding them. They were also made aware of the social realm stroke victims live in Portugal, their low incomes and frequent barriers to social participation, such as depression or isolation. Apart from the personas, students were given a file with information on Inclusive Design, Design & Emotion and Stroke. They were also given the guidelines for AP design.

For design development, we have relied on Munari's (1981) process, but adapted it to account for emotion analysis. The first task was for students to thoroughly analyze their user's living context, concerns and expectations drawing from the information provided in the persona cards.

The first interesting output from the workshop was that students found themselves referring to personas by their name (e.g. "Miss Arminda", rather than "the user", or even "the lady").

After the analysis to each persona's profile, concerns, and expectations, students were to simulate task performance to analyze not only ergonomics, but also the emotional responses along the task performance timeline. All personas presented hemiplegia, meaning students had to simulate task performance using one hand alone. Some groups also used gloves to simulate low dexterity or other contraptions, such as wrapping up their hands with cloths in order to restrain finger or hand movement. The most frequently mentioned emotions coming out of task simulation were *frustration* and *distress*.

To provide context for the description of the workshop, we will give a brief account of each persona and his/her concerns:

- Mrs. Maria de Jesus is bedridden and she is a former cook. It takes her a long time to peel vegetables, but she says the task gives her great pleasure. She wished she had a peeler that was easier for her to use. Monthly income: 436 euro.
- Mr. António Moreira, widow and former electrician, complains about the time it takes him every morning to put his socks on. He is afraid to bend down, feel dizzy and fall while performing this task. Monthly income: 208 euro.
- Mrs. Arminda Catarino has always been a housekeeper and likes to do things on her own. She does not own a washing machine and she is now having trouble in washing the pans. Monthly income: 180 euro.

Carlos Abreu	
Idade: 49 Est. civil: Casado Filhos: 1 Sit. profissional: Empregado Profissão: Proprietário de quiosque Valor do salário: 520 euros Escolaridade: 6.º ano Localidade: São João da Madeira	Lado dominante: Direito AWC: Há 8 meses Sequelas: Hemiplegia direita Grau de dependência: Dependência ligeira

Apertar os botões é um caso sério. Às vezes tenho que pedir à minha mulher e ela, coitada, já me ajuda tanto... Lá na fisioterapia deram-me umas coisas para ajudar a abotoar, mas eu não me dou com aquilo. Ainda não aprendi bem a usar a mão esquerda e aquilo nem sequer dá para todos os botões. Disseram-me para pôr velcro na roupa, mas não me apetece nada ter a roupa toda cheia de velcro e notarem-se os botões despertados...

Quotidiano:
 Arranja-se sozinho de manhã, toma banho sozinho e caminha com a ajuda de uma canadiana até ao quiosque que fica perto de casa. Volta ao fim da tarde e gosta de se sentar com o filho para o ajudar nos trabalhos de casa.

Problema:
 O casaco é mais fácil de abotoar porque os botões e as casas dos botões são grandes, mas custa-lhe muito apertar os botões do resto da roupa (calças e camisa) porque só pode usar uma das mãos e essa mão não tem muita destreza.

Figure 1. Example of persona used in the workshop (Note: the picture in the copy given to students was not blurred).

- Mr. Carlos Abreu is still working in his kiosk and his wife helps him with his daily tasks. It takes him a lot of time everyday to put his shirt on because he has difficulty in buttoning up. He wishes he could do this alone so as not to be such a burden for his wife. He furthermore states that the existing button hooks do not suit his needs – he says they are too difficult to handle. On the other hand, he is not comfortable with the *apply-Velcro-all-over-your-clothes* option. Monthly income: 520 euro (Figure 1).

- Mr. Manuel Casalinho is quite independent for a stroke victim, but he has a sick wife to look after and sometimes, when he has to sew a button on his own, he finds it difficult. It bothers him that he can do so many things, and then have trouble with this task. Monthly income: 453 euro.

After analyzing the problem both ergonomically and emotionally, students set out to look for existing solutions. They were asked to do a thorough research and analysis on existing products for each task, but also to look for parallel solutions in other typologies of objects, or even in nature. Whenever possible, students found the actual APs for the task they were analyzing and tested them.

Figure 2. Each group's proposal: a) Mrs. Maria de Jesus: a tray to peel vegetables while lying in bed; b) Mr. António Moreira: a long shoehorn made out of existing objects so that anyone could build one of these at home; c) Mrs. Arminda Catarino: a set of three fun 'spongy' balls to help hold the pans in the sink; d) Mr. Carlos Abreu: a seamless and easily portable low cost button hook; e) Mr. Manuel Casalinho: a device to help hold the fabric and the button along with a magnifying glass.

All groups found that the existing solutions were not suitable for their users. They also found existing APs to be very expensive and that many were not appealing.

After this first research and analysis phase – which took almost half the time for the entire workshop duration –, students set out to come up with solutions. In doing so, they were asked to have it very clear for them what they wanted to provide the users with. Based on their first analysis to the information they were given in each persona, some groups found their user's problem was about the time spent performing the task, while others, for instance, found that task performance was about providing an entertaining experience and that time of performance was not an issue. This was done through a weighted and comparative analysis of the personas' concerns, attitudes and goals.

Again, for all stages in the workshop, groups presented their findings, conclusions and design options to the class. The design ideation was encouraged to include several real scale mock-ups to allow interaction, and students were also encouraged to draw on a 1:1 scale to allow a closer visualization of how their designs were turning out. By the end of the workshop each group had developed a solution (Figure 2).

For the final workshop session we invited a freshmen design class to attend the final presentations. Each group was encouraged to present their project using storytelling, so as to make the audience resonate with both the user's problems and the work process carried out by each group over the two weeks. All the presentations were very successful.

In the end, each student wrote their individual letter to

the person they had been working for. Depending on students, letters were more or less formal. Many students showed they resonated with users' problems and some even thanked users for making them aware of the enormous challenge which a task they take for granted might be to a stroke victim. One of the frequent themes that came out of the letters was the pride students felt in their designs, and some students said they wished they could meet the users to learn about his/her opinions on the solutions and to further develop them, so they would exactly respond to users' needs. Finally, the vast majority expressed their conviction that their project would bring quality of life to the user.

STUDENTS' OPINIONS

After the workshop was over, we sent the questionnaire to every student. Fourteen students filled in the questionnaire. Most students had not previously engaged in an Inclusive Design project with account for emotions (72%), and none had ever gotten a brief presented in this way to them (persona). Most students, though, found it beneficial (92%). Most students also reported having created empathy with their users (86%) (Figure 3). They valued the quantity of information provided by each persona and said they got insights from the personas about what is life after a stroke. Two students reported that they found the information contained in the personas to be still insufficient and they would have liked to have been given more data to work on. One student reported that the workshop helped him realize that suffering a stroke does not account for homogeneity, because these personas were very distinct from each other due to their personalities and the ways they feel about different aspects of life. Students felt this method allowed them to carefully consider the emotions of the users they were designing for (86%) (Figure 3).

When asked, in an open-ended question, about what types of emotions they tried to design for, students' answers included: *a pleasurable experience, relaxation, comfort, nostalgia, confidence and delight through beautiful objects*. Some students answered their efforts were employed the other way around, i.e. to try to eliminate possible *frustration or anger*.

Figure 3. Graphics illustrating students' opinions on the effects of the methods used in the workshop.

Eight students (57%) reported having some feeling towards the user they had addressed. They reported *empathy, respect, curiosity, caring, dedication, affection, pity and admiration*.

All students said they had taken into account and used the guidelines for AP design they were given at the beginning of the workshop (Figure 3). One student said these guidelines were helpful because the design project was 'special' and that the guidelines alone gave information about the users. Other student said the guidelines were 'fundamental' for the design process. And other students gave other types of positive feedback, such as the guidelines being helpful for organizing time, for orientation, or for being very straight-forward.

Finally, students were asked about the writing of the letter. Most found it beneficial and saw it as an opportunity to engage in a more profound way with the users, and also to be able to directly explain what their project was without using the usual technical language they use with teachers or companies they work for. The biggest difficulty for students was to chose the type of language they should use in the letter (formal vs. informal) – students sought personal contact, but at the same time were not at ease with writing an informal letter.

FURTHER ANALYSIS

According to Ortony et al. (1988), empathy is not an emotion, but there are, however, "empathetic emotions". In the authors' framework these go by the name of "Good-will emotions" which are related to *fortunes-of-others*. These emotions imply that the one experiencing the emotion has or constructs "at least a partial model of the other person's plans and goals" (Ortony, et al., 1988, p. 92).

During task simulation at the first stages of the workshop students reported having experienced *frustration* and *distress*. These are both emotions which emerge as a response to an undesirable event. The students did not have a background in studying emotions, yet, according to their answers to the questionnaire, they reported having tried to elicit emotions which, according to the framework by Ortony et al. (1988), are on the opposite side of these negative experiences, such as *delight* as opposed to *distress*.

Task simulation and knowledge about a real person's problems (persona) also helped to raise empathy through enhancing sense of reality which, in the end, triggered students' *respect*, *curiosity* and *admiration* towards the person they were addressing due to the judged praiseworthiness of these users' actions in regard to their daily challenges.

Ortony et al. (1988) state that short-term **A**-goals (Active-pursuit goals) might be established for the realization of **I**-goals (Interest goals). By empathizing with users' concerns, students were able to experience **I**-goals which motivated their short-term **A**-goals, i.e. to devise appropriate and adequate solutions to meet the interest of these users' well-being. Our intention is that by providing a rich emotional experience in the workshop, students might feel compelled to adopt this posture in the future in other design projects as well.

DISCUSSION

Most literature on designer-user empathy reports cases where actual users are present during design development (McDonagh, Thomas, et al., 2009). To that end, participatory design for empathy building is more efficient, because users can constantly be providing feedback on project progress and are always around to answer questions designers might have. However, we believe we could compensate, to some extent, for actual users' absence through storytelling, our adaptation of personas and simulation. Moreover, since the workshop facilitator (first author) was deeply aware of each persona's case, she could provide students with further information that was not given in the persona card.

We believe this empathy that was born within students made them extra-careful about the design they were creating, and that this justifies their cautious account for the guidelines for AP design they were given.

Moreover, since all personas – in accordance with Portuguese reality – had very low incomes, students empathized with this constraint as well, and considered this within *product ecologies*, since they were able, amongst other things, to account for the price of their proposals.

The results of the workshop also seem to suggest as true that – as stated by Eisenberg et al. (1999) – empathy building might indeed promote prosocial behavior, and that the methods we have used during the workshop, having promoted empathy building, have also made students more aware of designers' social responsibility.

CONCLUSION

In our opinion, the approach was very successful at all levels. And it was so, we believe, due to 7 main factors:

- A thorough knowledge of stroke victims, their physical, emotional and psychosocial concerns, as well as a deep understanding of the social realm of these persons on the facilitator's part (previous user research);
- The adoption of storytelling to inform students, and the encouragement of the use of storytelling by students themselves;
- The emphasis put on the research and analysis stages of the workshop, giving students time to really think about and resonate with users' problems;
- The adoption of direct communication channels between designers and users (personas and letters), which gave students the extra-responsibility for their 'designerly' actions;
- The quality and commitment of the class, where all students were deeply engaged in the workshop activities;

- The encouragement of almost daily public discussions, making every group engage in other groups' projects;
- The establishment of several constraints to each project, causing students to focus on the problems they were addressing.

We believe this method to have been very efficient in tackling the usual problems of available resources. It depends upon a great amount of work to be done previously to the workshop implementation (research with users), but it might only take one person to do it – who will later assume the role of facilitator in the workshop –, thus minimizing costs.

In the occasions when participatory design may indeed be possible, we would suggest the adoption of these empathy-building methods could enrich the use of participatory design techniques.

The entire workshop's empathy building methods raised the sense of reality and strength of cognitive unit, mentioned by Ortony et al. (1988), and the weight of responsibility over students' shoulders, who in the end also had to personally address the users through a letter explaining their actions, choices, hopes and concerns, leading them to engage in a profound way with users they had not actually met.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Universidade Lusíada do Porto for welcoming our workshops, and particularly to Alexandra Amorim who helped us carry out the workshops with her Design III classes. The authors would also like to thank the valuable contributions of the anonymous reviewers for the final version of this paper.

REFERENCES

- Cardoso, C. And P.J. Clarkson (2012). Simulation in user-centred design: Helping designers to empathise with atypical users. *Journal of Engineering Design*, Vol. 23, 1, 1-22.
- Correia de Barros, A. (n.d.) Assistive products – Engineering, design and development. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal.
- Correia de Barros, A., C. Duarte, et al. (2011a) Crossing data: Where do users' preferences come from?. *Proceedings of the Include 2011 Conference*. London, UK, HHC-RCA. Available at: http://include11.kinetixevents.co.uk/rca/rca2011/paper_final/F372_2189.DOC
- Correia de Barros, A., C. Duarte, et al. (2011b) Fear as a design brief. *Proceedings of the Include 2011 Conference*. London, UK, HHC-RCA. Available at: http://include11.kinetixevents.co.uk/4dcgi/prog?operation=detail&paper_id=373
- Demirbilek, O. and H. Demirkan (2004) Universal product design involving elderly users: a participatory design model. *Applied Ergonomics*, Vol. 35, 361-370.
- Desmet, P. and E. Dijkhuis (2003) A wheelchair can be fun: a case of emotion-driven design. *Proceedings of the 2003 international conference on Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*. Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA, ACM, 22-27.
- Desmet, P., K. Overbeek, et al. (2001) Designing products with added emotional value: development and application of an approach for research through design. *The Design Journal*, Vol. 4, Issue 1, 32-47.
- Dong, H., P. J. Clarkson, et al. (2005) Critical user forums - an effective user research method for inclusive design. *The Design Journal*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, 49-59.
- Eisenberg, N., I. K. Guthrie, B. C. Murphy, S. A. Shepard, A. Cumberland and G. Carlo (1999). Consistency and development of prosocial dispositions: A longitudinal study. *Faculty Publications, Department of Psychology*, Paper 103. University of Nebraska – Lincoln.
- Eisenberg, N., N. D. Eggum and L. Di Giunta (2010). Empathy-related responding: Associations with prosocial behaviour, aggression, and intergroup relations. *Social Issues and Policy Review*, Vol. 4, Issue 1, 143-180.
- Erickson, T. (1995). Notes on design practice: Stories and prototypes as catalysts for communication. In: J. Carroll (Ed.), *Scenario-based design: Envisioning work and technology in system development*. New York: Wiley, 37-58.
- EUSI (2003) European Stroke Initiative Recommendations for stroke management - Update 2003. *Cerebrovascular Diseases*, 16, 311-337.
- Forlizzi, J. (2007) *Product ecologies: Understanding the context of use surrounding products*. School of Computer Science. Pittsburgh, PA, Carnegie Mellon University. PhD.
- Koupric, M. and F. Sleeswijk Visser (2009). A framework for empathy in design: Stepping into and out of the user's life. *Journal of Engineering Design*, Vol. 20, Issue 5, 437-448.
- Hoening, H., D. H. Taylor Jr, et al. (2003) Does assistive technology substitute for personal assistance among the disabled elderly? *American Journal of Public Health*, Vol. 93, Issue 2, 330-337.
- Manning, B., B. Altemeyer and S. Benton (2011) Sustainable social innovation by design: breaking down the boundaries. *Proceedings of the Include 2011 conference*, London, UK.
- McDonagh, D., J. Thomas, et al. (2009) Empathic design research: disability + relevant design. *Proceedings of the 8th European Academy of Design Conference*. The Robert Gordon University, Aberdeen, Scotland, 310-315.
- Munari, B. (1981) *Das coisas nascem coisas*. Lisboa, Edições 70. [Original title: *Da cosa nasce cosa*]
- Næss, I. R. and T. A. Øritsland (2005) Inclusive, mainstream products. *Proceedings of Include 2005 Conference*. London, UK.
- Nicolle, C. A. (1999) USERfit - Design for all methods and tools. *COST 219bis Seminar Human Aspects of Telecommunications for Disabled and Older People*. Donostia, San Sebastian, Spain.
- Ortony, A., G. L. Clore, et al. (1988) *The Cognitive Structure of Emotions*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

Pruitt, J. and T. Adlin (2006) *The persona lifecycle: keeping people in mind throughout product design*. San Francisco, USA, Elsevier.

Pullin, G. (2009) *Design meets disability*. Cambridge, MIT Press.

Storni, C. (2010) Multiple forms of appropriation in self-monitoring technology: Reflections on the role of evaluation in future self-care. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, Vol. 26, Issue 5, 537-561.

Traustadóttir, R., & Rice, J., G. (2012) Vulnerability at the intersection of poverty and disability. *Vulnerable Groups & Inclusion*, North America, 3, jan 2012. Retrieved January 31st from: <http://www.vulnerablegroupsandinclusion.net/index.php/vgi/article/view/9172/19267>

World Health Organization (2008) *Global burden of disease: 2004 update*. Geneva, Switzerland.